

Comparison of average diametric growth and radial growth of *R. solani* in *A. marmelos* essential oil.

peated four times with three replications each time.

Treated petri plates were incubated at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The data were computed by the formula $3.14 \times r^2$ (area measurement technique). The average diametric growth was always less than total radial growth (see figure).

Differences of a given growth ranged between 0.99 and 25%. When inhibition was 50% with the diametric growth measurement method, the same growth was only 25% by the area measurement method.

The difference increased from 0 to 50%, then decreased from 51 to 100%—the difference at 51% corresponds to the difference at 49, etc. There is a consistent 0.02% decrease between two adjacent units calculated by the area measurement method.

The method holds good for both sporulating and nonsporulating fungi. When fungal growth was irregular, however, this method was not accurate either. □

Joint infection of rice by *Sclerotium oryzae* Catt., *Sclerotium rolfsii* Sacc., and *Monographella albescens*

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During disease surveys of several foothill and upland ricefields in four districts of Manipur 1985-86, we noticed cases of sheath rot (ShR) fungus *Monographella albescens* (Thumen) Parkinson, Sivanesan and Booth associated with stem or foot rot disease. We collected 100 ShR-

diseased rice plants randomly from Imphal, Thoubal, Bishnupur, and Senapati districts. Those that also showed symptoms of stem- and foot rot-disease were separated and the disease isolated on potato dextrose agar (PDA).

Potted rice plants were inoculated at the late boot stage with 5-d-old cultures of *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*; control plants were treated with PDA medium alone. When disease symptoms appeared, prepared mycelial fragments from a 6-d-old culture of ShR fungus were sprayed on both diseased and control plants. Inoculated plants were maintained at 90% relative humidity.

Only two sclerotium-producing fungi, *S. oryzae* and *S. rolfsii*, were consistently associated with ShR (Table 1). The association of *M. albescens* with *S. oryzae* was higher than with *S. rolfsii*.

Rice plants infected with either *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii* were significantly more susceptible to ShR fungus (Table 2). □

Table 1. Association of *M. albescens* with *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*. Manipur Agricultural College, Imphal, India, 1985-86.

District	Plants analyzed (no.)	<i>M. albescens</i> association (%) with	
		<i>S. oryzae</i>	<i>S. rolfsii</i>
Imphal	100	8	2
Thoubal	100	5	4
Bishnupur	100	10	3
Senapati	100	6	3

Table 2. Severity of *M. albescens* on rice plants infected with either *S. oryzae* or *S. rolfsii*. Manipur Agricultural College, Imphal, India, 1985-86.

Source of infection	<i>M. albescens</i>		Disease incidence (%)
	Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (no.)	
<i>S. oryzae</i>	20	19	95
<i>S. rolfsii</i>	20	17	85
Control	20	5	25
LSD (0.05)	-	3	-

Influence of carbendazim concentration on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *Rhizoctonia solani*

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We studied the effect of different concentrations of carbendazim on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *R. solani*.

The culture filtrates of *R. solani*